

TERMS THAT REPRESENT A PATHOLOGICAL CONDITION IN CLINICAL TERMS AND THEIR SPECIFIC CHARACTERISTICS

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ANNOTATION: This thesis focuses on clinical terms that are widely used in medicine and their characteristics that represent their pathological condition. In this case, clinical terms are analyzed with examples of Greek and Latin expressions, their translation, their use in the present.

KEYWORDS: clinical terms, adjective elements (AE), inflammation, edema, rash, lunatism, nephritis, gastritis

The main task of the term (Latin terminus-border) is to express the scientific concept in one sense, in the form of exactly one word. The terms represent concepts of scientific and scientific technology, different from words in the artistic, literary language used in everyday life. In short, is a form of conclusion of a particular scientific theory. Clinical terms are a basic system of medical terms. Clinical terminology is the thousands of names and terms encountered in disease testing, disease history writing, textbook and instruction work. For the skillful, productive and effective use of clinical terms, it is necessary to know the means of making words of ancient Greek, since clinical terminology is widely used in medicine.

The role of Latin and medical terminology in the good assimilation of Clinical Sciences by students in medical universities is of incomparable importance. In this, mainly clinical terms occupy a special place. The study of clinical terminology is based on the analysis of individual components known as term elements. Let's dwell on the most used suffixes in clinical phrases.

the suffix-*ismus* has several meaningful structures. In particular, let's dwell on terms of the non-inflammatory nature. *Botulismus* - food poisoning (*botula*-sausage, horsemeat). *Somnambulismus* - is sleepwalking (lunatism).

In addition -the suffix *ismus* *Alchogolismus*-we can see the expression of the meaning in the character of alcohol addiction.

- the suffix *itis* indicates diseases of an inflammatory nature:

Gastritis - is inflammation of the gastric mucosa. *Nephritis* - is inflammation of the kidney. Such clinical phrases are pronounced in the vernacular as follows:

Nephritis-nephritis, *gastritis*-gastritis

the suffix-*oma* is added to the base of the tissue names to mean swelling from that tissue: *Lipoma* - is a safe tumor that develops in adipose tissue. *Myoma* - is a safe tumor made up of muscle tissue.

In addition, the suffix-*oma* is expressed by an increase in pressure, in addition to the meaning of edema. *Glaucoma* - is an eye disease that characterizes an increase in the internal pressure of the eye.

the suffix-*ema* occurs in the names of diseases in various characters:

Erythema-redness of certain parts of the skin due to blood flow. *Empyema* - is a rash of pus inflammation of the cavity (accumulation of pus in any cavity of the body).

the suffix-*osis* means that it is associated with diseases in the non-inflammatory character, the ability of the organism to change or above the norm, and is reflected in the following clinical terms:

Leucocytosis-an increase in white blood cells (leukocytes) in the blood. *Acidosis* - is an increase in acid in the blood and tissues. - the suffix-*iasis* denotes chronic but non-inflammatory diseases of long-term Origin:

Nephrolithiasis - is a kidney stone disease (nephrolithiasis). *Elephantiasis* - refers to the meanings of pathological tissue growth and development (elephantiasis) associated with the dimming (tick-like chick-like) of lymph.

In fact, such clinical terms are also pronounced in everyday life and among the people as follows:

Nephrolithiasis – neprothias *Elephantiasis* - elephantias.

Separately, the use of suffixes and prefixes in the making of clinical terms, the process of their translation into Uzbek or other languages, expresses a wider meaning than its own meaning. This makes it convenient for clinical terms to be used in its Latin, Greek form.

Thus, in our article we have outlined our opinions and reflections on the terms that represent the pathological condition in clinical terms, their construction using suffixes and the peculiarities of the terms. We have demonstrated the meaning and content of clinical terms through annotations, and in this we have analyzed clinical terms with facts from the clinical terms of Latin and medical terminology science.

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